

2.1 CONNECTING HORIZONS *precis & objectives*

In Brief. To explore these basic dynamics sustaining interconnected populations and memories, CONNECTING HORIZONS plans to look at our deep past and surviving present to map the emergence and disappearance of connectivity. Using statistical, network, and simulation approaches, the project identifies how interaction horizons emerge, persist, or collapse, and how cultural practices are maintained or lost through time. In doing so, we reveal both the fragility and resilience of past connectivity, showing how populations sustained social and material links despite environmental uncertainty and shifting landscapes. Overall, the project lays the groundwork for a new understanding of long-term inter-community interaction, offering tools and insights essential for **interpreting connectivity, memory, and cultural change across deep time**.

Core Hypothesis. At the core of CONNECTING HORIZONS the radical but, in light of the research-historical insights, necessary hypothesis that mobility, habitation and transport dynamics of populations is primarily **driven by collective memory dynamics**. Current archaeological data interpretation lack the perspective of addressing past and present behavioural change through the dynamics of forgetting and cultural loss, hampering insights from correlations with other data sources capturing complex climatic extremes and hazards difficult to unearth from the archaeological record. Hence, we require novel approaches to crafting the dynamical interpretation of long distant transport, as are novel analysis of archaeological ‘voids’ and the empirical grounding on empirical facts from the anthropological, ethnographic, historical record, together held by past and new cognitive science insights. This proposition and its implications are certain to challenge many archaeologist and cultural evolution academics working on human/environment relations.

2.2 Project Implementation

CONNECTING HORIZONS follows an integrative strategy combining three well-established research domains: (a) palaeohazards, including climate extremes, diseases and volcanic eruptions; (b) palaeolandscape morphology, with a focus on transport corridors, material sources and habitat suitability; and (c) walk-based communities, mapping movement, memory, exchange and risk-avoidance strategies. Crucially, these three domains overlap, providing the multidisciplinary foundation for the project’s five work packages following our main research questions.

WP1 combines hazards and subsistence strategies to examine how variability in natural hazards constrains ecological niches through time. **WP2** complements this by focusing on palaeohydrology, assessing how landscapes respond to floods and droughts during climatic extremes, and how riparian habitats sustain refugia, enable aggregation, and facilitate—or disrupt—transport corridors. From the population perspective, **WP3** investigates the vulnerability of walk-based long-distance transport and material exchange, identifying conditions under which connectivity becomes discontinuous. **WP4** builds on these insights by integrating palaeoclimatic models with archaeological and behavioural evidence, adding an often-invisible layer of group immunology and disease dynamics to refine interpretations of population change. Finally, **WP5** is developed alongside all other WPs, synthesising their outputs to model collective memory dynamics and the encoding—or loss—of knowledge about past disasters, landscape navigation, exchange systems, resource distributions, diseases and trust networks (FIG. 2).

FIG. 1 Diagram summarising the three main areas providing five WP

FIG. 2 Gantt chart illustrating the general project timeline, hiring periods, Work Packages (WP) and relevant submission and fieldwork campaigns

WP1: NICHE - SUSTEINANCE and HAZADS

Objective: to construct incorporate the sustenance strategies in cases of extreme weather and hazards impacts into niche reconstruction simulations in order to identify the suitability of the landscapes around known archaeological sites.

Methods: WP1 is divided into four interlinked sub-packages. **(I) Niche stability and marginality** examines how habitats that appear suitable under mean climatic conditions become marginal once climatic fluctuations are taken into account, integrating palaeohazard data derived from high-resolution palaeoclimate reconstructions (including outputs from the ERC **PIONEER** project (1)) with geological records of extreme events. **(II) Extremes: frequency, duration and variability** focuses on how the frequency, duration and variability of extreme events can be inferred from climatic records across different regions that serve as analogues for the palaeolandscapes under study, following a “Franken-reconstruction” of the Pleistocene based on well-documented Holocene extremes (2). **(III) Cross-cultural and archaeological scarcity adaptations** investigates subsistence behaviours in highly variable environments characterised by alternating periods of abundance and scarcity, drawing on cases such as highly variable pine harvesting in the interior basins of North America (3), whale strandings along specific northern coastlines and fire-shaped landscapes in the Australian interior (4). **(IV) Palaeo transport corridors** are incorporated into niche-suitability simulations by mapping known archaeological sites onto reconstructed landscapes and analysing their proximity and connectivity to transport corridors (5), with particular attention to walkable coastlines, mountain passes and valleys, as well as seasonal constraints such as snowfall, muddy or swampy ground, and arid landscapes with limited water availability (6).

On the archaeological side, the work builds on existing semi-standardised resources, including the **ROAD** database developed by the Out-of-Africa **ROCHEE** project (7), which synthesises published Afro-Eurasian archaeological evidence dated between 300,000 and 20,000 BP. This is complemented by regionally focused datasets on long-distance material provenance from Mesolithic Europe, (8, 9) the Epipalaeolithic Middle East and Caucasus (10, 11) and the East and South African Late Stone Age (12, 13). Climatic extremes are assessed using outputs from **CHELSEA–TraCE21k**, a palaeoclimatic simulation with 1 km² spatial resolution and monthly outputs averaged over 100-year intervals (14), enabling high-resolution estimates of climatic variability at specific archaeological sites up to 21 kys ago. For the crucial 20kyr-40kyrs other paleo climate simulations will be used, albeit at lower resolutions.

On the ethnographic side, WP1 draws on the **eHRAF World Cultures** database (15) as a core standardised resource, supplemented by targeted literature reviews and selective fieldwork in regions where walk-based mobility remains, or until recently remained, the dominant mode of transport. These include the Okavango Basin, the Australian interior, the North American Great Basin and the Northern Andes. Together, these data provide a cross-cultural baseline for mobility, exchange, mnemonic practices and hazard-coping strategies, enabling systematic mapping of environmental variability, biohazard exposure and landscape stability at relevant temporal and spatial scales.

Finally, on the modelling side, material use, abundance and accessibility are analysed by integrating archaeological provenance data with spatial models of raw-material distribution and landscape accessibility. Rather than treating materials as passive markers of movement, the project explicitly models how material properties and accessibility actively shaped mobility decisions, route selection and the stability of exchange links, particularly under conditions of scarcity or environmental stress.

Expected Outcomes: WP1 will deliver the first fully integrated, openly accessible empirical dataset linking long-distance transport, landscape structure, climatic variability, hydrology and hazard exposure for walk-based societies across deep time. This dataset will provide the empirical backbone for subsequent modelling work, enable comparative analyses across regions and periods, and establish a reproducible standard for studying connectivity and archaeological voids. By transforming heterogeneous evidence into a coherent analytical framework, **WP1 lays the groundwork for mechanistic inference of connectivity emergence, stabilisation and loss.**

Staff: (PD1+PD3+PI) led by PD1. The ethnographical side of human adaptation to extremes will be done in collaboration with PD3, and how these sustenance strategies can be modelled as habitat suitability maps. As the PI, I will vertebrate the work and focus on the resonances between collective memory dynamics and frequency of hazards and abundance impact.

WP2: WATER - EXTREMES and TOPOGRAPHY

Objective: to reconstruct the spatio-temporal dynamics of water availability and topographic constraints under climatic extremes, and to determine how floods, droughts and the stability or disappearance of water bodies shaped mobility, connectivity and landscape use in walk-based societies.

Methods: WP2 investigates water as a critical mediator between climate variability, landscape structure and human movement. Methodologically, the work is organised around three tightly integrated components: **(I) Floods and droughts: frequency, duration and variability**, which maps climatic extremes onto the abundance or scarcity of water across landscapes by modelling hydrological responses in explicitly non-linear ways; **(II) Palaeofluvial reconstructions**, which examine the configuration of water bodies near archaeological sites at the estimated times of long-distance transport activity; and **(III) Water-body stability and disappearance**, which integrates the previous components to assess how reliable water sources were under extreme climatic conditions. **(IV)** Outputs from these components, together with long-distance transport evidence from WP1, are compiled into a standardised dataset mapping transport evidence, environmental variability, and proximity to water bodies and their long-term stability.

WP2 quantifies the frequency, duration and variability of hydrological extremes by integrating high-resolution palaeoclimate reconstructions with geological and geomorphological evidence of flooding and drought, complemented by Holocene environmental records used as analogues (16–20). This approach identifies regimes of recurrent hydrological stress and clustering of extreme events that may have intermittently disrupted mobility corridors or rendered otherwise suitable habitats temporarily inaccessible. Rather than treating floods and droughts as isolated events, WP2 models them as temporally structured processes with cumulative effects on landscape accessibility and collective memory of risk. Palaeofluvial reconstructions are then used to map the evolution of river systems, wetlands and floodplains under changing climatic and topographic conditions. Drawing on geomorphology, sedimentary records and digital elevation models, WP2 reconstructs river stability, avulsion patterns and corridor persistence through time, explicitly linking these dynamics to topography and identifying how valleys, basins and mountain passes channelled movement or amplified hydrological vulnerability.

WP2 further analyses the stability and disappearance of water bodies—lakes, springs, wetlands and groundwater-fed refugia—focusing on thresholds beyond which water sources could no longer sustain necessary ecological functions, became unreliable, or vanished entirely. Finally, WP2 curates and publishes an integrated dataset on long-distance transport, the **PALEOPATH** pilot database (Pleistocene Archaeological Long-distance Origin: Provenance Analysis and Topography–Hydrology), developed in collaboration with Dr Jeremy Beller. **PALEOPATH** standardises information on site location, chronology, palaeoclimate, hydrology, topography and material-provenance distances.

Expected Outcomes: WP2 will produce a dynamic, hazard-sensitive reconstruction of water availability and topographic constraint for walk-based populations across deep time. Outputs include spatially explicit models of flood and drought prone landscapes, reconstructions of palaeofluvial networks and water-body stability, and quantitative indicators of hydrological reliability. And finally the **PALEOPATH** dataset standardising vulnerability to hazards, proximity to transport corridors, water-body variability, and evidence of long-distance transport.

Staff: (PD2 +PD1 +PI) led by PD2, with a strong background in hydrology modelling and with experience integrating climate data and landscape analysis, ideally with a basis in topography, geomorphology or palaeoenvironmental recreation. PD1 will assist PD2 in the simulation of paleohydrology variability and co-create the **PALEOPATH** dataset.

WP3: MOVEMENT - TRANSPORT CORRIDORS and MATERIALS

Objective: The objective of WP3 is to reconstruct how walk-based movement, material availability and exchange practices structure transport corridors and interaction networks, and how these dynamics shaped the emergence, persistence and breakdown of connectivity across landscapes when impacted by different hazards.

Methods: Methods. WP3 focuses on movement and exchange as core mechanisms linking landscape constraints, resource distribution and social interaction. Methodologically, the work is organised around three interdependent components: **(I) walk-based movement across landscapes**, which systematically analyses the ethnographic record alongside physiological research to characterise the range and variability of mobility strategies through cross-cultural comparison; **(II) material use, abundance and accessibility**, which examines what materials are transported over long distances, what drives and constrains such transport, and how stable these practices are through time; and **(III) gathering places and exchanges**, which investigates large-scale aggregation sites among walk-based hunter-gatherers where exchange and information transfer were likely to occur. Together, these components formalise how movement decisions, resource opportunities and social aggregation produced structured transport networks over deep time.

WP3 adopts a systematic cross-cultural framework that explicitly parameterises walk-based mobility rather than assuming it. Ethnographic evidence on long-distance movement, transport modes, exchange frequency, material loads, aggregation rhythms and encounter rates is compiled and tabulated into a standardised comparative dataset, allowing variability in mobility and exchange strategies to be quantified (3, 10, 21–24). Crucially, WP3 moves beyond the ethnographic “focal year” by capturing multi-year and intergenerational dynamics, enabling assessment of the resilience, loss or retention of long-distance transport and exchange practices, associated collective memories and technical expertise, as well as disease-avoidance behaviours linked to mobility. Targeted fieldwork in three walk-based case-study regions is essential for validating and refining these parameter estimates, assessing behavioural change under scarcity, environmental stress or epidemiological pressure, and documenting memory-based decision-making rarely captured in written sources.

These empirically grounded parameters are embedded in spatial movement models, where walk-based mobility is simulated using cost-surface and corridor analyses grounded in topography, hydrology and seasonality. Digital elevation models, palaeohydrological reconstructions and ethnographically informed physiological constraints are used to generate probabilistic transport corridors linking sites, resources and aggregation points, while accounting for seasonal constraints such as snow cover, flooding, aridity and swampy ground. Finally, archaeologically and ethnographically informed gathering places are modelled as network nodes where movement, material circulation and social interaction converged, allowing WP3 to evaluate how disruptions to aggregation dynamics contributed to the contraction or collapse of interaction horizons.

Expected Outcomes: WP3 delivers the first integrated reconstruction of walk-based transport corridors that explicitly link ethnographical evidence with movement costs, material availability and exchange practices. Key outputs include tabulation of transport modes, quantitative assessments of material-driven mobility, and the identification of aggregation nodes and gathering times critical for sustaining connectivity. These results provide essential inputs for subsequent modelling of probabilistic transport networks, collective memory and network stability, and enables a mechanistic interpretation of long-distance transport patterns and their disappearance in the archaeological record.

Staff: WP3 will be led by PD3, with expertise in cross-cultural comparison and tabulation and parametrisation of behaviour inferred from the ethnographic record. PD3 also shall lead fieldwork research to cross-validate the inferences from the ethnographical record. The PI, together with PD1 and PD2 will use these tabulated values to reconstruct movement *in silico*.

WP4: BIOHAZARDS - PALEOINMUNOLOGY and PALEOMEDICINE

Objective: to reconstruct how biohazards, infectious diseases and immunity-related practices influenced transport, exchange networks and landscape use, and to determine how pathogen pressure interacted with scarcity, migration and connectivity in walk-based societies.

Methods: WP4 addresses biohazards as an often-invisible but powerful driver of connectivity and avoidance, integrating recent advances in palaeogenetics, palaeoimmunology and landscape modelling. Methodologically, the work is organised around four interrelated components: **(I) palaeogenetics of diseases;** **(II) linking disease dynamics to scarcity and migrations;** **(III) pathogen landscapes;** and **(IV) immunity practices and community exchanges.** Together, these components enable the modelling of disease not merely as background risk, but as a dynamic force shaping movement, memory and interaction horizons.

First, **palaeogenetics of diseases** leverages recent breakthroughs in the recovery and sequencing of ancient DNA and proteins from human remains and sediments to map the presence and spread of pathogens through time (25, 26). WP4 synthesises published palaeogenetic datasets and integrates them with archaeological chronologies and ethnographically derived analogues. These reconstructions provide empirical constraints on pathogen prevalence and dynamics, even where direct genetic evidence is sparse.

Second, **connecting diseases to scarcity and migrations** examines how disease outbreaks intersected with climatic stress, nutritional scarcity and large-scale population movements—factors known to drive many malnutrition-related epidemics in historical contexts (27, 28). Importantly, this research explicitly investigates biohazards in relation to the contraction, redirection or collapse of mobility corridors simulated in WP2 and WP3.

Third, **pathogen landscapes** are reconstructed by combining palaeogenetic evidence with climatic, hydrological and ecological data to identify environments conducive to vector-borne pathogens, such as mosquito-rich wetlands, tick-prone ecotones or seasonally flooded landscapes. By treating pathogens as spatially structured landscape features rather than random shocks, WP4 provides a more realistic account of disease risk. Finally, **immunity practices and community exchanges** investigates how socially transmitted knowledge related to immunity—such as avoidance behaviours, medicinal practices and culturally embedded health strategies (27)—circulated through exchange networks, modelling how disease risk reshaped behaviour, settlement choices and long-term patterns of encounter and avoidance. Using ethnographic and archaeological analogues, WP4 explores how participation in long-distance exchange could both increase exposure to pathogens and facilitate the spread of immunity-related knowledge (29). These dynamics are explicitly linked to collective memory processes, allowing the project to model how disease experiences were remembered, encoded and acted upon at the community level.

Expected Outcomes: WP4 will deliver the first integrated framework linking paleodisease evidence, environmental conditions and mobility dynamics in deep time. Key outputs include spatial reconstructions of pathogen-risk landscapes, models of disease–scarcity–migration feedbacks, and empirically grounded scenarios of how biohazards influenced connectivity and archaeological voids. These results will provide essential inputs for subsequent modelling of memory dynamics and network stability, and will position biohazards as a central explanatory variable in the archaeology of connectivity.

Staff: WP4 will be led by the PI and supported by one postdoctoral researcher with expertise in palaeogenetics, palaeoimmunology or bioarchaeology, ideally with experience integrating genetic, environmental and archaeological data.

WP5: MEMORY and VOIDS - STATISTICS and ABSENCE

Objective: The objective of WP5 is to develop the theoretical, statistical and modelling framework that links collective memory dynamics to archaeological and demographic voids, integrating evidence from all other work packages to infer the emergence, fragility and collapse of connectivity across landscapes.

Methods: WP5 constitutes the conceptual and analytical backbone of CONNECTING HORIZONS, drawing together empirical inputs from WPs 1–4 and translating them into testable models of memory-driven connectivity and absence. Methodologically, the work is organised around four tightly coupled components: **(I) a brief history of collective memories; (II) evidence of absence and archaeological and demographic voids; (III) walkers' networks, encounters and fragility; and (IV) landscape voids, hazards and communities.** Together, these components enable the project to move from heterogeneous data to unified inference.

First, **a brief history of collective memories** establishes the theoretical foundations for modelling memory in deep time. Drawing on cognitive science, cultural evolution and historical anthropology, this component synthesises how collective memory is formed, maintained and lost, and how mnemonic technologies, repetition and connectivity stabilise or destabilise remembered knowledge (30–34). These insights provide the formal basis for translating qualitative concepts of memory into measurable, dynamic variables compatible with archaeological inference. Second, **evidence of absence, archaeological and demographic voids** develops statistical tools for distinguishing between absence caused by taphonomic or sampling bias and absence reflecting genuine behavioural avoidance or population withdrawal (35–37). Building on recent advances in Bayesian inference from incomplete data, WP5 formalises when and where absences in the archaeological record can be interpreted as meaningful signals. This component directly integrates outputs from WPs 1–4, including environmental marginality, hydrological instability, transport disruption and biohazard pressure, to test competing explanations for void formation. Third, **connecting walkers' networks, encounters and fragility** models population movement and interaction as encounter-based networks whose stability depends on frequency of contact, redundancy of routes and memory-supported expectations of safety and resource availability. Using agent-based and network models, WP5 explores how small perturbations—such as hazard clustering, disease outbreaks or loss of key routes—can trigger cascading failures in connectivity (38, 39). This component explicitly links individual movement decisions to large-scale network collapse or persistence.

Finally, **connecting landscape voids, hazards and communities** synthesises environmental and social drivers to explain how specific landscapes become persistently avoided or later reoccupied. By integrating hazard histories, hydrological change, pathogen landscapes and memory decay, WP5 reconstructs how communities encoded risk into collective memory and how this encoding shaped long-term patterns of landscape use. This approach reframes archaeological voids as dynamic outcomes of interacting environmental pressures and social memory, rather than static absences.

Expected Outcomes: WP5 will deliver a unifying theoretical and statistical framework for interpreting archaeological and demographic voids as products of collective memory dynamics and connectivity fragility. Key outputs include formal models of memory-driven avoidance, Bayesian tools for inference from absence, and integrative simulations that reconstruct the co-evolution of hazards, movement and memory. By synthesising results from all other work packages, WP5 produces the central explanatory architecture of CONNECTING HORIZONS.

Staff: WP5 will be led directly by the PI, reflecting its integrative and theoretical nature, with targeted support from the postdoctoral researchers contributing data and domain-specific expertise from WPs 1–4.

2.3 Feasibility, Risk Management and Suitability of the PI

CONNECTING HORIZONS is designed to balance demonstrably feasible research activities with high-risk, high-gain components that have the potential to transform how long-term human connectivity, memory and vulnerability are understood. The project deliberately combines robust desk-based synthesis, data integration and

modelling—where success is highly likely—with discovery-driven theoretical and inferential work that challenges entrenched assumptions in archaeology and the human sciences.

Several components of the project are low risk in terms of deliverability. The data-integration and synthesis activities in WPs 1–3 draw largely on existing, publicly available or semi-standardised datasets in archaeology, palaeoclimate, hydrology and ethnography. While these data are heterogeneous, the challenge lies in harmonisation rather than access. The PI has extensive experience working across fragmented datasets and standardising inconsistent measures, both in the natural sciences and in cultural-evolution research. Importantly, the success of these work packages does not depend on access to any single dataset or field site; multiple alternative data sources exist, ensuring redundancy and resilience against unforeseen data limitations.

The modelling components (WPs 3–5) rely on established, openly available computational tools, including agent-based modelling, network analysis and Bayesian inference. These approaches are well within the PI's expertise, grounded in a long-standing background in physics, complex systems and information theory. While some aspects of palaeoclimate and hydrological modelling require specialised knowledge, these are addressed through collaboration with domain experts and the use of mature, peer-validated model outputs (e.g. CHELSA–TraCE21k, ERC PIONEER). Computational infrastructure requirements are modest and compatible with standard institutional high-performance computing facilities.

The primary scientific risks of *CONNECTING HORIZONS* lie in its most innovative components—specifically, WP5, which develops a formal framework for interpreting archaeological and demographic voids as outcomes of collective memory dynamics rather than as noise or data absence. This is an explicitly high-risk endeavour, as it challenges long-standing interpretative conventions in archaeology and may lead to controversial conclusions regarding landscape avoidance, connectivity collapse and cultural loss. However, this risk is carefully mitigated by grounding inference in explicit statistical frameworks, Bayesian model comparison and simulation-based testing, rather than speculative interpretation. Even in the event that some hypotheses are falsified, the project will still deliver robust methodological advances in inference from absence and network fragility.

A related risk concerns the integration of biohazards and palaeodisease evidence (WP4), a rapidly evolving field where data availability is uneven across regions and periods. This risk is mitigated by treating palaeogenetic evidence as one input among several (alongside ecological, climatic and ethnographic proxies), and by explicitly modelling uncertainty and partial observability. The project is therefore resilient to uneven data coverage and is designed to produce meaningful results even under conservative assumptions.

Crucially, each work package is independently valuable and capable of producing publishable, field-advancing results on its own. The added value—and the main high-gain potential—emerges from their integration, which allows *CONNECTING HORIZONS* to move beyond descriptive accounts towards a mechanistic explanation of how memory, hazards, movement and landscapes co-evolved.

The PI is exceptionally well suited to lead this research. Trained originally in physics and astrophysics, with deep expertise in statistical modelling, uncertainty quantification and non-linear dynamics, the PI has subsequently developed an internationally recognised research profile in cultural loss, collective memory and human adaptability through competitive funding, including a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Global Fellowship. This trajectory uniquely positions the PI to bridge natural sciences, archaeology and anthropology—an essential requirement for the success of this project. The PI has a proven track record of independent project design, interdisciplinary leadership, mentoring of early-career researchers, and delivery of ambitious, theory-driven research. *CONNECTING HORIZONS* builds directly on these strengths while pushing decisively beyond them, making it both a natural continuation of the PI's work and a timely step change in scope and ambition.

In sum, *CONNECTING HORIZONS* is ambitious but feasible, risky where it matters scientifically, and carefully designed to ensure that even its boldest components yield substantial advances. The project is well matched to the PI's expertise, leadership experience and vision, and is positioned to deliver high-impact results that extend well beyond archaeology into the broader human sciences.

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Current research grants (Please indicate "No funding" when applicable):

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Funding source</i>	<i>Amount (Euros)</i>	<i>Period</i>	<i>Role of the PI</i>	<i>Relation to current ERC proposal¹</i>
Forest Landowner Education & Research Network (LEARN),	National Science Foundation, US	92,000	2026-02 2027-02	Modeller, coordinator, experimental designer	Investigating environmental biohazards, cultural adaptation and cultural learning

On-going / submitted grant applications (Please indicate "None" when applicable):

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Funding source</i>	<i>Amount (Euros)</i>	<i>Period</i>	<i>Role of the PI</i>	<i>Relation to current ERC proposal²</i>
None					

¹ Describe clearly any scientific overlap between your ERC application and the current research grant or on-going grant application.